

In Silico Trials:

An updated SWOT Analysis

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In Silico Trials: An updated SWOT analysis

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Introduction

The term

The term “*In Silico Trials*” indicates the use of computer modelling and simulation for the design, development, and regulatory approval of new medical products, including drugs, devices, or Advanced Therapeutic Medical Products (ATMPs). The term will always be capitalised in the text to represent it as a neologism. The term has been criticised by some experts who use the term trial not in a colloquial sense but with the narrow meaning proper of regulatory jargon. By writing capital initials, we stress that this is a new term with the meaning we define for it. In the regulatory context, we recommend the term *in silico* methodology¹ to avoid ambiguity. We do not endorse the term “model-informed drug development” because it reflects the narrow scope that some drug regulators see for *in silico* methodologies: a method that can inform but not replace experiment and is used only in the development (preclinical or early clinical phase). We are also not keen on the rigid separation by product type; the boundaries between drugs, biologicals, and devices are becoming increasingly blurred. Thus, we favour terminologies that do not narrow to a single product type.

The context

In Silico Trials have the potential to de-risk and accelerate the development of safer, more efficacious products. While computer modelling can be used in many ways during the entire lifecycle of a new medical product, here we focus on its use to refine, reduce or replace the experimental testing required during the development and de-risking process. While some authors refer to *in silico* experiments (i.e., [Kameo 2020](#); [Jansen 2023](#); [Guillem 2023](#)), here we will reserve the term “experiment” to physical studies conducted *in vitro*, *ex vivo*, or *in vivo*.

The terms Reduce, Refine, and Replace (3R) are borrowed from the community working on alternatives to animal testing, but here, they are used in a slightly different and much broader way. *Replace* indicates when the quantity of interest is predicted with a model rather than being measured/observed in a controlled *in vitro*/*in vivo* experiment. *Reduce* indicates the use of computer modelling and simulation to reduce the size/duration of the experiment, for example, to reduce the number of patients that need to be enrolled in a clinical study. *Refine* means using the computer model combined with an experiment to make the latter more ethical or useful. Controlled experiments can be conducted *in vitro* or *ex-vivo* (e.g. bench tests of a medical device, tests of biocompatibility with cell cultures, anatomical studies on cadavers), *in vivo* on animals, or in humans. Thus, *In Silico Trials* can be used in nine possible cases: to refine, reduce, or replace experiments done *in vitro*, *in vivo* on animals, or *in vivo* on humans. In ([Viceconti 2021](#)), we provide an extensive list of possible contexts of use for computer models in all nine categories.

The credibility of a model is paramount, especially when it aims to replace an experiment. The ASME technical standard VV40:2018² define credibility as “the trust, established through the collection of evidence, in the predictive capability of a computational model for a context of use”. Here, we prefer to use a narrower definition. We define *credibility* as the highest possible predictive error the model may commit compared to the value measured/observed in the experiment it aims to complement or supplement. Assessing model credibility is a complex technical topic, but some well-established

¹ *In Silico Methodology* is defined as “any use of CM&S as, at any level, a regulatory decision support tool on new medical products for which marketing authorisation is requested, whether medical devices, medicinal products, or others.” Viceconti, M. et al. (2024). Introduction. In: Viceconti, M., Emili, L. (eds) *Toward Good Simulation Practice*. Synthesis Lectures on Biomedical Engineering. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-48284-7_1.

² <https://www.asme.org/codes-standards/find-codes-standards/assessing-credibility-of-computational-modeling-through-verification-and-validation-application-to-medical-devices>

guidance³ and technical standards⁴ are now available. For examples of credibility assessment of some *In Silico* trial models, see ([Curreli 2023](#)) or ([Aldieri 2023](#)).

Besides assessing model credibility, the use of *In Silico* Trials poses several operational issues that our community of practice has now addressed and summarised in a Good Simulation Practice (GSP) position report, published as an open-access book that can assist companies and institutions planning to adopt such new methodologies ([Viceconti and Emili, 2024](#)).

Thus, everything seems now in place for biomedical companies to consider using *In Silico* Trials. However, like any other strategic business decision, the company's management must carefully balance the pros and cons before jumping on this new bandwagon or considering moving in-house the use of *in silico* methodologies done so far through external consultants. A thorough, well-documented Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats analysis (SWOT) is essential for such decisions. Developing such a SWOT analysis requires considerable work and a certain degree of specialism, which is not always available in every company. Thus, this consensus report developed by the In Silico World Community of Practice aims to provide companies considering adopting *In Silico* Trials with an extensive and well-documented generic SWOT analysis as a basis for adoption in their own use cases.

About the In Silico World Community of Practice

The In Silico World (ISW) project is a research initiative funded by the European Commission in the frame of the Horizon 2020 programme. For more information on the project, see <https://insilico.world/>. ISW aimed to lower the barriers that slowed the adoption of *In Silico* Trials. Over the last four years, ISW has made a substantial contribution in this direction, helping the consolidation of the regulatory pathways for *In Silico* Trials in the EU market or providing resources for credibility assessment. A key development of ISW is the ISW Community of Practice (ISW_CoP) on Slack⁵, a private social network open to all practitioners with an educational or professional interest *in silico* medicine.

Adopting *In Silico* Trials is a disruptive change, and, like all major changes, it encounters some resistance. To overcome this resistance, we thought of a safe, pre-competitive space where all experts and practitioners from academia, industry, and regulatory agencies can ask for advice, exchange information, develop best practices, and discuss anything else that can make the use of *In Silico* Trials an accepted practice. The community is configured as a forum where members can join teams and collaboratively work on shared goals, projects, concerns, problems or topics. The community is invitation-only: in this way, we assure that only experts with a professional interest in *in silico* medicine can access the channels and resources. Of course, anyone can ask for an invitation. To date, 721 experts are members of the community, including individuals from:

- Large biomedical companies such as Medtronic, Smith & Nephew, Pfizer, Johnson and Johnson, Innovative Medicine Initiative, CSL Behring, Ambu, RS-Scan, Corwave EN, Zimmer Biomet, Novartis, Bayer, ATOS, Biogen, Agfa, Icon PLC, Amgen, ERT, Exponent, etc.
- Biomedical SMEs such as Nova Discovery, Lynkeus, Obsidian Biomedical, Quibim, Mediolanum Cardio Research, Voisin Consulting, CRM-Microport, Mimesis srl, H.M. Pharmacon, MCHCE, etc.
- In Silico Solution Providers such as Ansys, InSilicoTrials Technologies, 3DS, ASD Advanced Simulation & Design GmbH, Kuano-AI, Aparito, Chemotargets, Digital Orthopaedics,

³ <https://www.fda.gov/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/assessing-credibility-computational-modeling-and-simulation-medical-device-submissions>

⁴ <https://www.asme.org/codes-standards/find-codes-standards/assessing-credibility-of-computational-modeling-through-verification-and-validation-application-to-medical-devices>

⁵ <http://insilicoworld.slack.com>

ExactCure, Materialise, Bio-CFD, Matical, FEOPS, 4RealSim, Exploristics, Synopsis, Virtonomy, Cad-Ferm Medical, etc.

- Regulators and standardisation bodies such as FDA, DIN, BSCI China, NICE, Critical Path Institute, AQUAS, etc.
- Clinical research institutions such as Istituto Ortopedico Rizzoli, Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center, Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland, University Hospital Graz, Charité – Berlin University Medicine, Centro Nacional de Investigaciones Oncológicas, Aspirus Health Care, Universitätsklinikum des Saarlandes, European Society for Paediatric Oncology, etc

Because of the importance that the ISW_CoP is playing in the development of *in silico* medicine, the VPH Institute (<https://www.vph-institute.org/>), the international not-for-profit organisation that represents the *In Silico* Medicine research community worldwide, has agreed to take on the moderation of the online community of practice and continue operating it after the end of the ISW project on December 2024.

Purpose of the document

The targets of this document are the executives of biomedical companies, large and small, who must decide if, when, and how much to invest in *In Silico* Trials. By providing them with a thorough, well-documented SWOT analysis, we aim to facilitate this task and favour more extensive investments toward their adoption.

ISW Project will publish the final full-length consensus document on behalf of the entire CoP that contributed to its compilation as an Open Access document to ensure the widest possible circulation. However, we do not exclude the possibility that parts of the document are also published through other channels to be agreed upon among the authors.

As the document is being revised, we are adding the names of those who edited it as authors and the generic reference to the ISW_CoP to include all those who contributed to the debate.

SWOT Analysis - Strength

Develop medical products more ethically and at lower costs

Ethical costs

Our societies have growing ethical concerns about how medical products are developed and tested. The primary drivers are the ethical concerns related to animal testing, but also human experimentation is an object of continuous debate (e.g. for paediatric or pregnant women populations). Both are perceived as a necessary evil, at best. *In silico* methodologies have their own ethical concerns (for example, see Chapter 7 in ([Viceconti and Emili, 2024](#))), mostly related to privacy issues associated with using sensitive data to develop models. Still, they are perceived as much less controversial than *in vivo* testing. The progressive refinement, reduction, and even replacement of animal and, in some cases, human testing with *in silico* methodologies may drastically change the public perception of biomedical companies, regulatory agencies, and the medical products themselves. Adopting investigation methods subjected to less ethical scrutiny also indirectly reduces costs for ethical approval procedures by ethical committees monitoring animal and human experimentation.

Financial Costs

To obtain a summary of the financial costs involved with the experimentation done during the development of medical products, we used the support of ChatGPT (GPT-4 architecture) to synthesise

such a complex aspect. The choice might seem odd, so here we explain it. It is not unusual in reports of this kind to see fairly old statements supported by one or two cherry-picked references, ignoring many others that would provide figures that contradict such statements. To avoid this, we would need to systematically review the literature for each statement in this section, which would require a significant effort. AI tools like ChatGPT automate, to some extent, such systematic reviews, providing statements that are the compendium of hundreds or thousands of references.

The most evident benefit of replacing experimental studies with *in silico* methodologies is reduced development times and associated costs. First, we asked for the average cost for preclinical studies to test a new medical product.

“The cost of preclinical studies to test a new medical product can vary widely depending on several factors, including the complexity of the studies, the type of product being tested (e.g., small molecule, biologics), and the specific requirements of regulatory agencies. However, here are some general estimates:

Average Costs for Preclinical Studies

1. **Basic Toxicology and Pharmacokinetics Studies:** Include initial safety testing, dose range finding, and pharmacokinetics. **Cost Range:** \$1 million to \$3 million.
2. **Good Laboratory Practice (GLP) Toxicology Studies:** Required for regulatory submission, these studies are more comprehensive and rigorous. **Cost Range:** \$2 million to \$4 million.
3. **Specialised Studies:** This includes genotoxicity, reproductive toxicity, carcinogenicity, and other specialised studies. **Cost Range:** \$500,000 to \$2 million per study.
4. **Animal Models and Efficacy Studies:** Efficacy testing in relevant animal models can be particularly costly for complex or novel therapeutics. **Cost Range:** \$1 million to \$5 million.

Total Preclinical Costs

The total cost for a complete set of preclinical studies typically ranges from **\$3 million to \$10 million**. This range can be higher for biologics, advanced therapies (e.g., gene therapies), or highly innovative products requiring extensive testing. [Source: ChatGPT⁶].

Then we asked about the average cost for clinical trials of new medical products: “The cost of clinical trials to test new medical products can vary significantly based on several factors, including the tested product (drug, medical device, ATMP), phase of the trial, the therapeutic area, and the complexity of the study design. However, here are some average cost estimates for new drug development based on recent industry data:

- Phase I Trials: These early-stage trials typically involve a small number of healthy volunteers or patients to assess safety, dosage, and side effects. Costs can range from \$1 million to \$5 million.
- Phase II Trials: These trials involve a larger group of carefully selected patients to evaluate the efficacy and side effects. Costs generally range from \$7 million to \$20 million.

⁶ When asked for the sources of this information, provided on July 6th, 2024, ChatGPT replied:

1. **“Tufts Center for the Study of Drug Development:** Provides insights into the costs and timelines of drug development, including preclinical studies.
2. **Pharmaceutical Research and Manufacturers of America (PhRMA):** Offers data on R&D costs, including preclinical stages.
3. **Contract Research Organizations (CROs):** Companies like Charles River Laboratories, Covance, and others often publish case studies and cost estimates for preclinical research. **Examples:** [Charles River Laboratories](#), [Covance](#).
4. **Industry Reports:** Reports from consulting firms such as Deloitte, PwC, and others provide in-depth analyses of R&D costs, including preclinical expenses. **Examples:** [Deloitte Life Sciences Reports](#), [PwC Health Research Institute](#).

These sources offer detailed information on the costs and factors affecting preclinical studies, providing a comprehensive understanding of the financial requirements for this stage of drug development”.

- Phase III Trials: These are large-scale trials involving hundreds to thousands of patients to confirm efficacy, monitor side effects, and compare with standard treatments. Costs can range from \$20 million to over \$100 million.
- Phase IV Trials: Post-marketing studies to monitor long-term effects and gather additional information on the product's risks, benefits, and optimal use. Costs for these studies can vary widely, typically ranging from \$2 million to \$10 million or more.

A comprehensive study by the Tufts Center for the Study of Drug Development estimated the average cost to develop and bring a new drug to market, including all clinical trial phases, at approximately \$2.6 billion. This figure includes the costs of failed trials and the cost of capital”. [Source: ChatGPT⁷].

Last, we asked for the average costs of *In Silico* Trials: “The cost of an *in silico* trial can vary widely depending on several factors, including the complexity of the model, the specific disease or condition being studied, the level of regulatory approval required, and the infrastructure and expertise needed to conduct the trial. However, estimates from various sources suggest the following ranges:

1. **Basic *in silico* trials:** These can cost from tens of thousands to a few hundred thousand dollars. Simpler models and less stringent regulatory requirements generally keep costs lower.
2. **Complex *in silico* trials:** For more advanced simulations involving complex diseases or high-fidelity models, costs can range from several hundred thousand to over a million dollars.
3. **Regulatory-grade *in silico* trials:** When these simulations are used for regulatory submissions, costs can be significantly higher, often reaching several million dollars due to the extensive validation and documentation required.

Specific numbers can include:

- **Simple pharmacokinetic/pharmacodynamic (PK/PD) models:** \$50,000 - \$200,000
- **Disease progression models or virtual patient cohorts:** \$200,000 - \$500,000
- **Regulatory submissions with extensive validation*:** \$1 million or more

The exact cost will depend on the trial's detailed requirements and the study's specific objectives” [Source: ChatGPT⁸].

⁷ When asked for the sources of this information, provided on July 6th, 2024, ChatGPT replied: “Here are some primary sources and references that provide detailed insights into the costs of clinical trials for new medical products:

1. [Tufts Center for the Study of Drug Development](#) (CSDD) - Tufts CSDD Report: A key report by the Tufts Center for the Study of Drug Development estimated the average cost to develop a new drug, including clinical trial costs. This report is often cited in discussions about drug development costs.
2. [Pharmaceutical Research and Manufacturers of America](#) (PhRMA) - PhRMA Publications: PhRMA provides comprehensive data and analysis on R&D costs, including clinical trials, through its annual reports and publications.
3. [Deloitte Life Sciences Reports](#) - Deloitte Insights: Deloitte publishes in-depth reports on the biopharmaceutical industry, including detailed analyses of clinical trial costs and trends.
4. [PricewaterhouseCoopers Health Research Institute](#) - PwC Analysis: PwC offers reports and insights into the costs and operational aspects of clinical trials, focusing on various factors influencing trial costs.
5. Journal Articles and Industry Publications:
 - "[Clinical Trials: A Methodologic Perspective](#)" by S. Piantadosi: This book provides a comprehensive overview of clinical trial methodologies, including cost considerations.
 - "The Cost of Conducting Clinical Trials": Articles published in journals such as *Clinical Trials* and *Pharmaceutical Medicine* often discuss detailed cost analyses.

These sources provide a robust foundation for understanding the costs associated with clinical trials and the factors that influence these costs”.

⁸ When asked for the sources of this information, provided on July 6th, 2024, ChatGPT replied: “The information provided in the previous response is synthesized from various industry reports, expert opinions, and case studies on the cost of *in silico* trials. Here are some primary sources and references that can provide more detailed insights:

- "The Cost-Effectiveness of *In Silico* Trials for Clinical Research" - This report by the Avicenna Alliance details the potential cost savings and investment requirements for *in silico* trials compared to traditional clinical trials.
- FDA and EMA Regulatory Guidance - Both the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and the European Medicines Agency (EMA) have published guidelines on the use of modeling and simulation in regulatory submissions, which provide insights into the validation and cost implications.

ChatGPT's figures are primarily influenced by the costs of developing medicinal products, on which there is ample literature on the Internet. For medical devices, they can be a bit overestimated. Here are the figures from a recent study on the US market: “In this economic analysis, the mean development cost for a novel therapeutic complex medical device was \$54 million (95% CI, \$25 million-\$200 million), excluding any post-approval studies that might be required. After accounting for the cost of failed studies and the cost of capital, the mean capitalised cost of bringing a novel therapeutic complex medical device to the US market was \$522 million (95% CI, \$205 million-\$3382 million). The key factors associated with this cost were the phase transition probabilities: 46.9% for nonclinical to feasibility study, 48.0% for feasibility to pivotal study, 75.7% for pivotal study to FDA premarket approval submission, and 80.5% for FDA premarket approval submission to approval. The nonclinical development stage constituted the largest portion of the overall cost at 85.0%, while the FDA review stage had the highest phase transition probability, accounting for only a small fraction at 0.5%” ([Sertkaya 2022](#)). The other word of caution is that the average cost of *In Silico* Trials is based on much less public information than the other costs. **However, even considering all this, it is evident from these figures that when an experimental study can be avoided using an *in silico* methodology, the direct cost savings range between 30% and 90%.**

Reduce time to market

The average time to market for a new medicinal product typically ranges between 10 to 15 years. The discovery phase and the preclinical testing, on average, take 3 to 6 years. 1 to 2 years for phase I clinical testing, 2 to 3 years for phase II, and 3 to 4 years for phase III studies. Then, it takes 1 to 2 years for the final regulatory review and approval^{9,10}. The average time to market for medical devices is shorter, 1 to 7 years, depending on the class of the device and, thus, the regulatory pathway. Using the US market as a reference (because more documentation is available), a 510(k) Premarket Notification pathway (used when similar devices already exist on the market) can take about 6 months to 2 years^{11,12}.

On the contrary, a Premarket Approval (PMA) pathway (used for innovative, high-risk devices) may take 3 to 7 years¹³. In the authors' knowledge, there are not yet systematic studies on how effective *In Silico* Trials can be in reducing the time to market; **some experts suggest at least 50% reductions**. While putting a price tag on this is complex, according to McKinsey, for blockbuster drugs (those with annual sales exceeding \$1 billion), bringing a drug to market one year earlier can increase the net present value (NPV) by up to \$100 million to \$150 million¹⁴.

Rinse and repeat

But in the long term, we expect *in silico* methodologies to have a much more structural effect than a mere reduction of costs and time to market. One key difference between *in vivo* and *in silico* testing is that the latter can be repeated. When you repeat an *in vivo* experiment, you need to enrol different subjects, but in an *in silico* investigation, you can test different treatments on the same virtual cohort.

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- Industry Case Studies - Companies specializing in *in silico* trials, such as Insilico Medicine, Certara, and others, often publish case studies and white papers that include cost estimates and project examples.
 - Academic Research Papers - Journals such as the Journal of Pharmacokinetics and Pharmacodynamics and CPT: Pharmacometrics & Systems Pharmacology often publish studies that include economic evaluations of *in silico* trials.

For the most accurate and detailed information, referring to these sources and reviewing their published documents would be beneficial”.

⁹ <https://lifesciences.n-side.com/blog/what-is-the-average-time-to-bring-a-drug-to-market-in-2022>

¹⁰ <https://pharmaceutical-journal.com/article/feature/drug-development-the-journey-of-a-medicine-from-lab-to-shelf>

¹¹ <https://www.wolterskluwer.com/en/expert-insights/medical-device-outlook>

¹² <https://clarkstonconsulting.com/insights/2023-medical-device-industry-trends/>

¹³ <https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/device-advice-comprehensive-regulatory-assistance/how-study-and-market-your-device>

¹⁴ <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/life-sciences/our-insights/the-pursuit-of-excellence-in-new-drug-development>

While the contribution of failed products to the total development cost for a new drug is estimated at around 30% (DiMasi 2016), the attrition rate (proportion of drug candidates that do not successfully advance through clinical trials and regulatory approval to reach the market) is up to 90% (Hammel 2019). ***In silico* methodologies can drastically reduce attrition by comparing multiple options at each development step with modest cost increases.**

Another important difference is that models can be reused and refined for later in the development process. A good *In Silico* Trials tool can become a strategic asset for a biomedical company, refined over the years and then used at each step of the product development lifecycle.

Learn from failures

In Silico Trials can be used to gain mechanistic insight around safety or efficacy, for which may be difficult, if not impossible, to gain from experiments. For example, consider the case where an animal study shows that a new compound causes proarrhythmic cardiotoxicity. But to find out *why* this happens, it may take months or even years of additional testing. However, suppose I detect proarrhythmic cardiotoxicity *in silico* (Trovato 2022). In that case, the same computer model can easily show why such adverse effects occurred, which may help design another compound with the same intended effect but without such an adverse effect (Clark 2022). **With *in silico* methodologies, the development of medical products can move from a trial-and-error approach to a more mature test-and-refine process.**

SWOT analysis - Weaknesses

A debated paradigm for regulatory science

The relevance of this weakness largely depends on the strategic positioning of *in silico* methodologies. Since *in silico* approaches can be used over the entire lifecycle of a new medical product, their impact is modest when *in silico* methodologies are used to reduce, refine or replace preclinical experiments. In our experience, the regulators have few objections once one can prove that the *in silico* methodology can better estimate what might happen in humans than *in vitro* or *in vivo* animal experiments.

The other scenario where this concern has minimal impact is if your company is developing a new medical device to be sold in the USA market. The FDA-CDRH has clearly defined regulatory pathways for using *in silico* evidence in the marketing authorisation dossier of new medical devices. The lack of a central authority has slowed things a bit in Europe. Still, now that the IEC TC 62 has established the working group “PWI 62-5 - Establishing the credibility of computational modelling in the field of medical devices through verification, validation, and uncertainty quantification”, explicitly targeting the ASME VV40:2018, this should ease the acceptance by EU-notified bodies of the evidence of the credibility of computational results following the VV40.

The only area where we see difficulties is if your company plans to use *in silico* methodologies to reduce, refine or partially replace human testing. In this case, we strongly recommend undertaking the Qualification Advice for new methodologies that both FDA-CDER¹⁵ and EMA¹⁶ provide. This should reduce the risk associated with adopting such innovative methods.

¹⁵ <https://www.fda.gov/drugs/drug-development-tool-ddt-qualification-programs/clinical-outcome-assessment-coa-qualification-program>

¹⁶ <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory-overview/research-development/scientific-advice-protocol-assistance/opinions-letters-support-qualification-novel-methodologies-medicine-development>

Model development and validation costs are very high

The cost of developing new *In Silico* Trials is decreasing exponentially. Developing the first models was challenging and expensive, but new models that reuse a large part of the work done for the previous models can drastically reduce the development costs. The development cost will vary widely for some time, and putting a price tag on it is not easy.

Companies will also face a “make it or buy it” dilemma; in some cases, the pathophysiological knowledge of the disease of interest and of the mechanism of action of the new treatment is so strong in-house that developing their own *In Silico* Trials might be a wise investment, especially if the company expects to develop multiple products targeting similar diseases or leveraging on similar mechanisms of action. However, in many other cases, buying or renting the necessary tools and/or services from third parties is much more convenient.

A business model to be explored is when the biomedical companies own the experimental data required to validate the new model. Because validation can be the most expensive part of developing new *In Silico* Trials, biomedical companies can broker special deals where they get the use of the *in silico* methodology (or the obtained computational results) at discounted rates in exchange for the opportunity for the model’s developer to use the company data to validate their model up to the regulatory qualification.

Validation costs will be the bottleneck for some time. If the credibility assessment plan required by the regulator requires validation datasets available in the public domain or that can be produced anew with moderate experimental costs, that *in silico* methodology will be easier to adopt. Research funding agencies should consider supporting projects specifically aimed at producing validation collections, such as those recently released by the In Silico World Consortium¹⁷, that the industry needs to validate their *in silico* methodologies. However, joint efforts like the IHI programme should also consider funding such projects.

Mechanistic models are more reliable but need knowledge

The predictive models at the heart of any *in silico* methodology can be divided into two broad categories: knowledge-driven and data-driven. Knowledge-driven models are built starting from available (and reliable) mechanistic knowledge about the disease process's physics, chemistry, and pathophysiology (and of the target of action for the treatment). Using such mechanistic knowledge, a domain specialist manually builds the predictive model. This process is slow, complex, and requires extreme specialism, which is the main reason for the high development costs. However, when such mechanistic knowledge is available, knowledge-driven models are preferable because they are more reliable and explainable, and their credibility can be demonstrated once and for all.

The alternative is data-driven models. They are the only option when insufficient mechanistic knowledge is available to build a reliable predictor. On the other hand, data-driven models need large collections of high-quality data to train the predictor. As the development of machine learning predictors is progressively automated (with the so-called MLOps¹⁸), the development cost for a data-driven model will gradually shift toward collecting and curating the data. In the long run, we expect the data-driven models to become much cheaper to develop than knowledge-driven models. The catch is that most regulators are leaning toward a credibility assessment for data-driven predictors that require periodic retesting ([Bideault 2021](#)). So ultimately, what you save in development, you may spend on extra validation testing. In conclusion, we recommend that the choice between data-driven, knowledge-driven or hybrid approaches is entirely based on the availability of mechanistic knowledge and not on (short-term) economic considerations.

¹⁷ <https://insilico.world/datasets/>

¹⁸ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MLOps>

Computational efficiency and scalability issues

Today, one core hour on an HPC cluster costs between \$0.04 and \$0.12, depending on how you calculate it¹⁹. To the authors' knowledge, one of the most computationally expensive *In Silico* Trials is the BoneStrength simulator that predicts the efficacy of interventions to reduce hip fracture incidence in fragile elderly (La Mattina 2023). The code uses one million core hours to simulate a full-scale phase III clinical trial entirely *in silico*. Even in this case, the computational cost would “only” be \$120,000, which is negligible compared to any experimental study. In addition, many of these models can be made computationally more efficient using machine learning for surrogate modelling.

The scalability problem, in general, is limited to very special problems. For example, today's agent-based models (frequently used to model complex multicellular systems) can simulate some hundred million agents at most using the largest HPC systems. To model the whole body at the cell scale, one would need to model 300 billion agents. However, most untreatable problems can be accurately modelled using multiscale models at a fraction of the computational cost.

Thus, considering the constant growth of the computational power available through HPC centres and commercial public clouds, computational efficiency and scalability can be considered minor weaknesses.

Skill gaps

This is probably the biggest weakness of *In Silico* Trials today: relatively few people can be considered experts in this emerging discipline. Recruiting people with the necessary skills is and will remain challenging for some time. Higher education institutions are aware of the problems, and there is a growing educational offer around *In Silico* Trials (see, for example (Vander Linden, 2023)), both in terms of training at the master level and re-training for people already working in the industry. Still, it will take time to train enough people as the demand is growing exponentially. But this is also a good reason for biomedical companies to not sit on the fence. Those companies that can recruit the best experts will have a major competitive advantage, at least for some time. Alternatively, specialised companies offer *In Silico* Trials design and execution as a service in collaboration with the client.

A point of debate is how far we should go in adding elements of computational sciences and engineering to the curriculum of pharmacologists, biologists, and medical doctors. Beyond a certain point, this would require an extensive reorganisation of these educational curricula, which expands the scope for math and physics.

SWOT Analysis - Opportunities

The cost of drug development is unacceptably high

The high cost of development is preventing several scenarios. If *In Silico* Trials can drastically reduce such costs, these scenarios would become viable business opportunities. One is that of *precision medicine*. The idea is that one can develop new treatments for a disease that are particularly effective for specific subpopulations. This idea found its first applications in oncology, where the mutated genome of the cancer cells can inform the identification of highly specialised but effective druggable targets. However, precision medicine targets are now becoming broader and not limited to cancer or genomic information. We can imagine a future where, for each disease, there are many treatment options from which the doctor chooses the one best suited for that patient. The problem with this

¹⁹ <https://rescale.com/blog/the-real-cost-of-high-performance-computing/>

scenario is that each of these precision treatments would have a much smaller market. As for rare diseases, today's approach is to set very high sales prices to cover the high development costs, even for a limited number of target patients. But if we can drastically reduce the development costs, the selling price for these precision treatments would become reasonable, and a whole new set of business opportunities would open up.

Similarly, high development costs for rare (or ultra-rare) diseases may result in such high treatment sales prices that it may be commercially unfeasible for the company to proceed.

Time to market is unacceptably too high

Using computer modelling and simulation has since long reduced the time to market in several industrial sectors (e.g., [Rosova, 2020](#); [De Paula Ferreira, 2021](#)). As previously illustrated, it can take 12 years from conception to market for a drug²⁰ and up to seven years for medical devices²¹. This long time-to-market is responsible for the major financial components of the development costs, but it also carries other business disadvantages. The attrition rate is one major factor in such a high time-to-market ([Hay, 2014](#)). By simply improving the ability of preclinical studies to predict the clinical outcome, *In Silico* Trials have a huge potential to reduce attrition rates and, in general, the time-to-market of medical products.

Another specific issue related to reducing time to market is the response to epidemic emergencies. The COVID-19 crisis showed the importance of accelerated development and regulatory approval procedures. *In silico* methodologies did play a major role in the development of COVID-19 vaccines:

- *In silico* techniques enabled the swift identification of potential viral targets, such as the spike protein of SARS-CoV-2 ([Arshadi, 2020](#)).
- Advanced computational tools, including molecular dynamics simulations and machine learning, were used to predict the 3D structure of viral proteins ([Arshadi, 2020](#)).
- Computational models helped predict the efficacy and safety of vaccine candidates before clinical trials ([Russo, 2020](#)).
- *In silico* methodologies were used to optimise the formulation of mRNA vaccines, such as those developed by Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna ([Arshadi, 2020](#)).
- Virtual clinical trials and computer simulations of patient populations helped predict potential outcomes and side effects, which streamlined the design of real-world clinical trials. ([Arshadi, 2020](#); [Russo, 2020](#)).

The biomedical industry and the regulatory authorities have a moral imperative to ensure that future pandemics are handled with the smallest time-to-market humanly possible.

Revision of the Medical Device Regulation

The introduction of the Medical Device Regulation 2017/745 (MDR) has had a major impact on the EU medical device market. Not only does it require that most devices available on the market be recertified, but it also considerably extends the cases when a clinical assessment becomes mandatory. The limited penetration of *In Silico* Trials in EU medical device companies and the unclear regulatory value for evidence obtained *in silico* have limited the use of *In Silico* Trials to handle this crisis. However, notified bodies are becoming more open, as the ASME VV40:2018 has been cited as the proper standard for assessing the credibility of predictive models in various sources, including a recent ISO standard. Also, the recent establishment of the PWI 62-5 working group within the IEC

²⁰ <https://pharmaceutical-journal.com/article/feature/drug-development-the-journey-of-a-medicine-from-lab-to-shelf>

²¹ <https://www.medicaldesignandoutsourcing.com/fda-510k-clearance-de-novo-classification-cost-time-new-medical-product/>

TC 62 technical committee aimed to develop an ISO-IEC standard harmonised with the VV40 is helping in this direction. Thus, all medical device companies that sell in the EU market must expand their use of *In Silico* Trials to reduce the impact of the new MDR.

Rare diseases

In Silico Trials can transform the development of treatments for rare diseases into a viable business opportunity because of the reduction of development costs and the possibility of reusing components of the predictive model developed for one disease into another. For example, all rare diseases affecting the skeleton (osteogenesis imperfecta, achondroplasia, hypophosphatasia, etc.) share the same physiological layer used to model skeletal growth.

Other business opportunities

An extensive use of *In Silico* Trials along the entire product lifecycle could open new business opportunities in specific applications:

- **Treatment retargeting:** there are various cases where a treatment developed to treat one condition could be used to treat another. However, this retargeting requires, in many cases, a regulatory process that is not so different from the one that authorised the primary use. Using *In Silico* Trials, the model's physiological and mechanism of action layers developed for the original indication could be reused, with only adaptations, for the new target condition.
- **Comorbidities:** it is always challenging to investigate experimentally the presence of comorbidities or the possibility of adverse interaction between multiple drugs because, with experimental methods, there is always a trade-off between controllability and realism. But in *In Silico* Trials, you control 100% no matter how complex the phenomenon is being modelled. Thus, you can account for multiple disease progression layers and treatment models acting simultaneously.
- **Animal testing alternatives:** There is growing evidence that in many cases, *Silico Trials*, alone or combined with advanced *in vitro* methods such as organ-on-chip, can provide an estimate of the response of humans to a new treatment better than animal models.
- **Therapeutic equivalence:** various clinical and commercial reasons motivate the search for molecules that have a clinical effect equivalent to a commercially available drug. Today, therapeutic equivalence is investigated preclinically at the cellular scale. Then, pharmacokinetics is used to confirm that the bioavailability is equivalent. However, clinical equivalence is demonstrated only with clinical trials, which frequently fail because these preclinical studies are insufficient. However, if the clinical trials on the original molecule were used to validate the corresponding *In Silico* Trials, which can predict the effect of each molecule on the clinical manifestations of the disease, confirming the therapeutic equivalence *in silico* would involve a smaller risk that the clinical trial fails.
- **Diversity and effectiveness:** there is growing evidence that gender, social and ethnic diversities are not always adequately represented, introducing bias and gaps in clinical trials. It may be due to the difficulty of recruiting a cohort representative of all possible diversities. The recent issue with pulse oximeters is a good example²². Similar problems are at the root of the difference between efficacy and effectiveness, which is required for cost-benefit analyses. Using experimental methods, the only way to assess effectiveness is to run post-marketing surveillance, where you monitor the effect of the treatment without any selection and monitoring biases. But

²² <https://publichealth.jhu.edu/2024/pulse-oximeters-racial-bias#:~:text=In%20November%202022%2C%20an%20FDA,people%20with%20darker%20skin%20pigmentation>

that takes time and costs a lot of money, and it can be very disappointing if only at that stage you find out that your treatment, while effective, is not cost-effective. An excellent example of these kinds of biases is compliance. In controlled randomised clinical trials, there are all means to ensure compliance, but for drugs used not in hospital settings, lack of compliance is a well-known determinant of apparent poor effectiveness. Simulating the effect of patient compliance (or lack thereof) is simple in *In Silico* Trials. The same applies to cohort diversities; the challenge for *in silico* cohorts is to be statistically representative of the target population; simulating the treatment on a cohort of 300 Kg women is relatively easy. As far as we have the mechanistic knowledge to inform the physiological layer of our model with the effect that gender, ethnicity, poverty, or any other potential bias may have, it is easy to account for it.

SWOT analysis – Threats

We see four significant threats on the horizon that companies should consider as they plan their investments in *In Silico* Trials: culture, lack of harmonisation wait-and-see, and one big failure.

Cultural barriers

In the Open Access report “Regulatory Barriers to the Adoption of *In Silico* Trials”²³, the ISW consortium critically analysed the experience accumulated with two qualification advice procedures with the Scientific Advisory Working Party of the European Medicine Agency (SAWP- EMA), a Qualification Submission procedure with the FDA Center for Devices and Radiological Health (CDRH-FDA), and several less formal interactions with FDA, and European national medical device authorities. The report suggests that the core issue is that a good part of the scientific advice that guides the regulatory qualification of new methodologies is based on a social science epistemology that relies on a strict frequentist statistical inference. This is more marked in the regulators dealing with medicinal products and less in those dealing with medical devices. On the other hand, *in silico* methodologies make sense only if one operates under a physical sciences epistemology, which relies on Bayesian statistical inference. At the risk of trivialising a complex matter, for a frequentist, it is inconceivable that an experimental observation is replaced with a prediction made using some prior knowledge, whether explicit (from the laws of physics) or implicit (extracted from data with machine learning methods).

This profound cultural barrier will require time and commitment to overcome. In our opinion, the solution is to push for the interdisciplinarity of methodological scientific advice panels, which now include almost exclusively clinicians, pharmacologists, and pharmacometricians on the medicinal side of all regulatory agencies. We recommend extending these panels to include bioengineers, biophysicists, biomathematicians, and computer scientists. Initially, panel consensus will be difficult because of these cultural differences, but eventually, a middle-ground pragmatic epistemology will emerge, including predictive models when appropriate. Such a process is more likely to happen within the FDA than in Europe, where the separation of the regulatory authorities for drugs and medical devices will make this “cultural contamination” more difficult.

It will also take time (and constant pressure from policymakers on governmental organisations that tend to resist change by their nature). While this happens, such cultural barriers will be lower for medical devices than drugs, in the USA than in Europe, and for preclinical evidence than clinical ones. Adopting *in silico* methodologies will also be easier for situations where the experimental study is impossible for practical or ethical reasons. These include double blinding for surgically implanted devices, placebo arms when a treatment is available, rare diseases, etc.

²³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10948477>

Lack of harmonisation

Those with a long experience in the regulatory field will remember the days when the USA and the European Union had largely incompatible regulatory frameworks. Over the years, the various regulatory agencies recognised this was a problem in a growing global market and started to harmonise their procedures and technical specifications. Today, while significant differences remain, companies can “reuse” much of the work done to obtain marketing authorisation in one national market to pursue another nation.

Such harmonisation is now being challenged for everything related to *in silico* methodologies. The structural and political differences between the USA and the EU regulators constantly increase the disparity concerning these new methodologies. All the stakeholders are aware of this risk and are working to minimise it. Still, companies should be aware that right now, and probably for some time in the future, it will be easier to use evidence obtained with *in silico* methodologies in the USA regulatory system than in the EU one.

The wait-and-see threat

At the risk of trivialising a complex and rapidly changing landscape, the market leaders for medical devices compete primarily over innovation. In contrast, the pharmaceutical market is often cited as an example of an oligopoly, a market structure characterised by a small number of firms that dominate the market. Oligopolistic practices include market concentration, barriers to entry, pricing power, mergers and acquisitions, patent protections, lack of generic competition and interdependence. Insulin pricing is a known example of the adverse effects of these practices ([Herkert, 2019](#)). An effect of these differences between medical devices and drugs markets is that while MedDev market leaders have been leading the adoption of *In Silico* Trials, big pharma has, so far, invested much more conservatively in this methodology, primarily around drug discovery and preclinical testing.

However, this wait-and-see attitude is rapidly becoming a potential threat to pharma companies. In 2007, PricewaterhouseCoopers published a report entitled “Pharma 2020: Virtual R&D. Which path will you take?”²⁴, where they explained that because of the soaring burden of chronic disease, payers’ restriction of prescriptions, cost-benefit expectations were on the rise, blurring of healthcare forms, growth of developing world demand, growing focus on prevention, and higher risk aversion of regulators pharma companies had to move rapidly toward virtual R&D and *In Silico* Trials. The fact that after 17 years, parts of this analysis are still relevant reveals how these big players are struggling to cope with all these changes affecting the healthcare market. The difference is that now the price of waiting could be much higher.

Consider, for example, the case of Eli Lilly tirzepatide. The FDA approval of this diabetes drug for weight loss has driven up the market capitalisation of Eli Lilly by 37% in the first quarter of 2024²⁵. What would happen if a smaller company used *In Silico* Trials to find a valid bioequivalent and market it at a much lower cost? Eli Lilly is sending the cease-and-desist letters to all those who produced compounded versions of tirzepatide under the medication shortage regulation²⁶ confirms how worrisome such a scenario would be.

One big failure

There is also a potential threat opposite to the wait-and-see one. If some overenthusiastic companies, possibly exploiting the limited experience that some regional regulators or notified bodies may have

²⁴ https://www.pwc.com/gx/en/pharma-life-sciences/pdf/pharma2020_virtualrd_final2.pdf

²⁵ <https://www.globaldata.com/media/business-fundamentals/top-20-global-biopharmaceutical-companies-report-9-6-market-capitalization-growth-in-q1-2024-reveals-globaldata>

²⁶ <https://qz.com/eli-lilly-compounded-zepbound-cease-and-desist-1851622157>

in evaluating the credibility of *in silico* methodologies, would obtain marketing authorisation for a medical product that then post-marketing monitoring would demonstrate to be severely unsafe, this could fire back on the entire sector. Despite the thorough regulatory process, once every while, a defective medical product reaches the market. But in this historical moment, when *in silico* methodologies are the new kid on the block, if a massive recall such as those of Boston Scientific's pelvic mesh²⁷, DePuy Orthopaedics' ASR metal-on-metal hip replacement²⁸, or Bayer's Essure permanent birth control device²⁹ would be associated to incorrect evidence provided by an *in silico* methodology, this could push the *in silico* agenda years back.

Companies planning to adopt *in silico* methodologies should not try to cut corners but rather build confidence in these new methodologies within and outside the company.

The final word

We hope this document can help executives in large and small biomedical companies target their investments in *in silico* methodologies in a more informed way. We believe *In Silico* Trials are the future, but only the biomedical industry can decide if this is indeed the case.

Contributors

This document was developed as a consensus process among experts using the #insilicotrials_SWOT channel created for such purpose on the ISW Community of Practice on Slack (insilicoworld.slack.com). The following experts contributed to the consensus process:

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²⁷ <https://news.bostonscientific.com/fda-decision-on-transvaginal-mesh-for-POP>

²⁸ <https://www.drugwatch.com/hip-replacement/depuy/recall/#:~:text=DePuy%20Orthopaedics%20recalled%20its%20ASR,DePuy%20delayed%20the%20international%20recall>

²⁹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Essure>

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